

Factors affecting brand awareness: Case of food industry in Vietnam

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Abstract

Studying the factors affecting the level of brand awareness is one of the basic requirements for businesses to meet the needs of customers. In this research paper, the author has explored the theoretical basis related to brand and brand identity. Based on that, a research model was built with 05 independent variables and 01 dependent variable. The research results show the order of influence of factors on brand awareness: the Brand name factor has the largest beta coefficient (0.393), followed by the logo factor (0.352), slogan (0.352), Brand colors (0.145), Website (0.133). From that basis, the thesis makes suggestions on solutions for a firm of food industry in Vietnam.

Keywords: Brand Identity; Brand; Awareness; Brand Name; Logo; Slogan; Color; Website

1. Introduction

In the current economic context, the brand is considered one of the tools to measure and evaluate the business effectiveness of an enterprise. Therefore, investing in building a brand through various activities has become a concern for many businesses. Since entering the market until now, food industry in Vietnam has attracted a lot of attention from consumers in the target market. This research focuses on some typical firms in this industry such as Kim Cuong Food. From 2018 to the present, the company has achieved certain successes in terms of revenue, but still has limitations in terms of brand. One of the activities that needs improvement is the brand recognition system, moving towards the mission and goal of becoming a leading enterprise in Vietnam. In order to better understand the creation and development of its brand, the company has decided to conduct research on the factors influencing brand perception.

2. Theoretical basis

2.1. Brand concept

With the lecture on brand management by Nguyen Quoc Thinh (2018), the brand concept was presented: "Brand is one or a set of signs to identify and distinguish products and businesses; is the image of the product or business in the public mind."

2.2. Brand functions

- Functions of recognition and discrimination
- Information and instruction function
- Function to create perception and trust
- Economic function

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2.3. The role of the brand

Brands create images of businesses and products and services in the minds of customers and the public. Consumers will choose products through their feelings, through the messages that the brand conveys to consumers. Brand is the position and image of the product positioned in the customer's mind.

Brand as a commitment between businesses and customers, the public. When consumers choose branded products, it means that consumers have accepted and trusted in that product and brand. Thanks to that, the business has increased the perception and trust of customers. That of consumers; through brands (as vital signs) to identify segments of the market.

Brand brings many benefits to businesses: The ability to access the market easily, more widely; Goods bearing famous brands can be sold at higher prices, consumers are less discerning.

Brand helps attract investment, increase customer relationship. Once a well-known brand is established, consumers are no longer afraid to invest in the company's shares, which will be of more interest to consumers; Your customers will also be willing to cooperate in business, providing raw materials and goods for the business.

Brand is an intangible and very valuable asset of a business. When the brand becomes valuable people will be willing to make the transfer or transfer the right to use the trademark. The brand is the property of the business, the reputation of the brand as a guarantee of the consumer's profit.

Brand identity system: is a collection of brand elements and their representation in different media and environments. In essence, the brand identity system is all that consumers and the public can recognize and distinguish about a brand (usually just tangible elements).

2.4. Research model and hypothesis

Figure 1 Proposed research model

Brand name is one of the first elements that make us remember about brand. Without a brand name and logo, a business cannot make customers recognize its brand before hundreds of thousands of other products of competitors or buy products more easily. Research by Vo Huu Nhat Duc (2003), Tran Thi Huyen Trang (2010); Nguyen Thi Thuy Hang (2013), Foroudi et al (2017), Pham Ngoc Nhu Quynh (2021) show that: brand name is an important factor affecting the brand identity of customers. Based on the above, the proposed hypothesis is: Hypothesis H1: Brand name affects customer's brand recognition.

The tagline is an integral part of the brand, it occupies an equally important position in the brand. Research by Vo Huu Nhat Duc (2003), Tran Thi Huyen Trang (2010); Nguyen Thi Thuy Hang (2013). The research results show that the slogan factor is one of the factors affecting the brand awareness of customers with the BIDV brand. Based on the above study, the proposed hypothesis is: Hypothesis H2: Slogan affects brand awareness of customers.

Logo is a representative signal of a business, many people are familiar with logos of businesses and large corporations in the world. A logo can also be a signal that represents a type of business product. Research by Vo Huu Nhat Duc (2003), Tran Thi Huyen Trang (2010); Nguyen Thi Thuy Hang (2013), Pham Ngoc Nhu Quynh (2021) show that: Logo is an important factor affecting the brand awareness of customers. Based on the above bases, the proposed hypothesis is: Hypothesis H3: Logo affects customer's brand identity

Standard colors are colors that represent businesses or products, are applied to specifying all colors in visual information design, have an important effect in creating business impressions. Research by Tran Thi Huyen Trang (2010); Pham Ngoc Nhu Quynh (2021) shows that: Brand color is an important factor affecting the brand awareness of customers. Based on the above research, the proposed hypothesis is: Hypothesis H4: Brand color affects customer's brand identity.

For businesses in the technology age, a website is an extremely necessary tool. It brings a series of great utilities, making selling easier and faster than ever. Research by Foroudi et al (2017); Bright. N. N (2020) points out that: Website is one of the factors that help customers identify brands. Based on the above bases, the proposed hypothesis is: Hypothesis H5: The company's website has a positive impact on customers' brand recognition.

3. Research methodology

All collected data will be encrypted, entered and cleaned with the help of SPSS software. Official research data is collected by random sampling method; the sample is randomly selected with the probability of being selected for customers who have been using products of food companies in Vietnam. The minimum sample in comparison with numbers of items is 125. But, in order to increase the reliability as well as to remove the data that is not valid for the study, the author has collected up to 200 questionnaires. In which, there are up to 192 suitable votes, the author uses these votes to analyze through SPSS software

4. Research results

Table 1 Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the independent variable

Encoding	Factors	Variable correlation coefficient total	Cronbach's coefficient Alpha
BRAND NAME (TTH)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.857	
TTH1	Easy-to-read brand name	0.681	0.828
TTH2	Easy-to-remember brand name	0.638	0.842
TTH3	Impressive brand name	0.670	0.830
TTH4	Brand name at association	0.823	0.765
SLOGAN (SG)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.887	
SG1	Easy-to-understand slogans	0.710	0.870
SG2	Easy-to-remember slogan	0.807	0.834
SG3	Meaningful slogans	0.800	0.837
SG4	Attractive slogans	0.704	0.877
LOGO (LG)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.830	
LG1	Logos are easy to remember and have many meanings	0.653	0.788
LG2	Logos show the difference	0.659	0.785
LG3	Logos are easy to distinguish from brands other	0.719	0.756
LG4	Logo has high aesthetic	0.607	0.810

BRAND COLOR (MS)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.837	
MS1	Easily recognizable colors	0.646	0.807
MS2	Impressive colors	0.674	0.793
MS3	The color is easy to associate with the brand	0.647	0.805
MS4	Color has a special meaning	0.733	0.765
WEBSITE (WEB)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.911	
WEB1	The company's website is very specialized Karma	0.823	0.872
WEB2	The company's website is full of information	0.857	0.844
WEB3	The company's website is in sync with the image pictures and colors	0.790	0.902

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 5 independent variables ≥ 0.6 . Specifically: The brand name is 0.857; Slogan is 0.887; Logo is 0.830; Brand color is 0.837; The website is 0.911 so the scales are all very good. Total correlation coefficient of 19 independent observed variables ≥ 0.3

Table 2 Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of dependent variable

Encoding	Criteria	Coefficient of correlation of total variables	Coefficient Cronbach's Alpha
BRAND AWARENESS (NDTH)		Cronbach's Alpha = 0.940	
NDTH1	I easily recognize the brand name	0.850	0.926
NDTH2	I easily recognize the company's Slogan	0.827	0.929
NDTH3	I can easily recognize the company's logo	0.797	0.932
NDTH4	I easily recognize the color of love company brand	0.838	0.927
NDTH5	I easily recognize the company website	0.816	0.930
NDTH6	I easily recognize the company in the market school	0.799	0.932

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

Table 3 EFA analysis results for independent variable

Evaluation factor	Test value
KMO coefficient	0.845
The value of sig in Bartlett's test	0.000
Total variance extracted	73.223
Eigenvalue	1.345

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

The results of the Cronbach's Alpha reliability test of the dependent variable "NDTH" reached $0.940 > 0.6$ (good scale) and the total correlation of the observed variables was > 0.3 . Therefore, the dependent variable "NDTH" ensures reliability for inclusion in EFA analysis and subsequent tests.

Results of the first EFA: $KMO = 0.845 > 0.5$, sig Bartlett's Test = $0.000 < 0.05$, so factor analysis to explore EFA is appropriate. There are 5 factors extracted based on the criterion Eigenvalue = $1,345 > 1$, so these 5 factors summarize the information of 19 observed variables included in EFA in the best way. The total variance that these 5 factors extracted was $73.223\% > 50\%$, so the 5 factors extracted explained 73.223% of the data variation of 19 observed variables participating in EFA.

Table 4 Rotation Matrix

	Factor				
	1	2	3	4	5
SG2	0.862				
SG3	0.854				
SG1	0.798				
SG4	0.751				
TTH4		0.872			
TTH3		0.809			
TTH2		0.746			
TTH1		0.691			
MS4			0.813		
MS1			0.811		
MS2			0.770		
MS3			0.724		
LG3				0.817	
LG1				0.793	
LG2				0.768	
LG4				0.720	
WEB2					0.920
WEB1					0.895
WEB3					0.872

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

Table 5 EFA analysis results for dependent variable

Evaluation factor	Test value
KMO coefficient	0.581
The value of sig in Bartlett's test	0.000
Total variance extracted	77.148
Eigenvalue	4.629

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

The dependent variable “NDTH” includes 6 observed variables. From the table above, we see: KMO = 0.581 > 0.5, sig Bartlett's Test = 0.000 < 0.05, so EFA exploratory factor analysis is appropriate. The analysis results show that there is a factor extracted at Eigenvalue equal to 4,629 > 1. This factor explains 77.148% of data variation of 7 observed variables participating in EFA exploratory analysis.

Table 6 Evaluation of the fit of the model

Model	R	R ²	R2 correction	Estimated degrees standard deviation	Durbin- Watson
1	0.902 ^a	0.814	0.808	0.4486	2.030

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

The results of R² and R² adjusted to evaluate the goodness of fit of the model. The adjusted R2 value of 0.808 shows that the independent variables included in the regression analysis affect 80.8% of the variation of the dependent variable, the remaining 19.2% are due to out-of-model variables and random errors. The results of this table also give Durbin-Watson values to evaluate the phenomenon of first-order series autocorrelation. The value DW = 2,030, is in the range of 1.5 to 2.5, so the results do not violate the assumption of first-order series autocorrelation.

Table 7 Analysis results of regression coefficients

Model		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	Test value t	Sig.	Statistical	
		B	Error	Beta			Coefficient	VIF
1	Constant	-20.681	0.236		-11,362	0.000		
	TRIAL	0.498	0.049	0.393	10,082	0.000	0.660	1.516
	SG	0.269	0.044	0.237	60.181	0.000	0.684	1.463
	LG	0.516	0.054	0.352	9,538	0.000	0.735	1,360
	MS	0.227	0.058	0.145	3,883	0.000	0.724	1.382
	WEB	0.169	0.044	0.133	3,822	0.000	0.826	1.211

(Source: Author - Data processed from SPSS)

The normalized regression equation is shown below:

$$NDTH=0.393*TT+0.352*LG+0.237*SG+0.145*MS +0.133*WEB$$

5. Conclusion

First, the brand name solution: Maintain and further strengthen communication activities. Communication on Internet channels such as Facebook, Twitter... is also an effective and suitable brand communication solution for the company. The company can reach customers through those Internet channels to have a wider spread and take advantage of the advantages brought by those channels. The campaign takes advantage of the support communication channel from the staff. Encourage self-sharing of the brand communication of firms with employees

Second, solution about Logo: The logo is easy to remember and has many meanings, the logo shows the difference, the logo is easy to distinguish from other brands, the logo has high aesthetics. However, not stopping at satisfaction, food companies in Vietnam need to has updated and perfected its logo to match the changes over time of the market and other factors that make the logo a factor that helps customers easily identify and have a standing position in the hearts of customers. client

Third, slogan solution: So the solution to this problem is also to focus and promote brand communication, so that the Slogan is known to many customers. With simple and easy-to-understand content, slogan will help the company's brand approach closer to the public. At the same time, slogan should also appear more in the promotional activities of the business (including online and offline).

Fourth, brand color solutions: Enhance impressive communication to bring the brand name, logo, slogan to reach potential customers. Once memorized or impressed with those elements, the brand's orange-red image will automatically enter the customer's mind. Synchronize dominant colors in all corporate publications. Currently, in addition to the main factors, only uniforms and employee cards, especially product packaging, use the company's main colors.

Fifth, website solution: Currently, the company has its own website, which is considered appropriate and full of information. However, the operation of the website is not really effective in affecting the brand awareness level of customers. In order to improve the brand identity system and reach more customers, the company should focus on updating information, posting regularly to optimize the information on the website so that viewers can see the process. The operation process of food companies is always stable in both present and future

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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